

Title:

Mapping Mismatch: Perceived vs. Measured Diversity in Urban Activity Spaces

Abstract:

The study of segregation in activity spaces is undergoing a renaissance, driven by the increasing availability of geospatial data from mobile phones and social media. These new data sources have facilitated high-resolution spatial analysis of individual mobility patterns, offering insights into the diversity of visitors in different urban spaces. A key motivation behind this research is to foster social cohesion by designing inclusive spaces that encourage intergroup contact. However, amidst the enthusiasm for analyzing large datasets, an important nuance may have been overlooked—perception often plays a more significant role than objective measurements in shaping urban experiences. Yet, we know very little about the relationship between perceived and measured diversity in activity spaces.

This study examines this relationship by integrating GIS-based mobility modeling with survey-based perception data. We used mobility data from approximately 90,000 mobile phone users to model the spatial movement patterns of residents identifying as Asian, European, and Pacific. These mobility flows were analyzed to compute spatial diversity indices across neighborhoods in Auckland. To complement this geospatial analysis, we conducted on-street surveys to collect perception-based diversity assessments of these locations.

Our findings indicate that the alignment between measured and perceived diversity varies depending on the particular diversity metric applied. Additionally, spatial context and the perceived inclusivity of specific locations significantly influence this relationship. Furthermore, we observe differences in perception patterns between long-term residents (more than five years in New Zealand) and recent arrivals, suggesting that spatial familiarity and acculturation processes shape how individuals interpret urban diversity.